

Table.1. Matrix metalloproteinases classification

MMPs Classification

<i>Traditional classification</i>	<i>Numerical classification</i>	<i>Chromosomal localization</i>	<i>Group of substrates enzymes</i>	<i>General biological effect</i>	<i>Reported eye localization</i>	<i>Eye implicated processes</i>	<i>Ref</i>
Collagenases							
Collagenase-1	MMP-1	11q22-q23	EMC Substrates Collagen (I, II, III, VII, VIII, X), Entactin, Laminin, Gelatin, Elastin, Fibronectin, Aggrecan, Brevican Neurocan, BM-40, Decorin, Vitronectin, Entactin/ Nidogen, Tenascin, Perlecan, CTGF, Link protein, Myelin basic protein, Fibrin, Fibrinogen	Mediate normal ECM turnover, migration of keratinocytes, re-epithelialization, cell migration, platelet aggregation, increase in the bioavailability of IGF-1, cell proliferation, pro-inflammatory effect, and PARP1 activation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Corneal stroma ○ Optic nerve head ○ Cultured RPE cells ○ Trabecular meshwork ○ Aqueous humor 	AMD Eye Processes - Development of soft drusen- early AMD - The directional shift in the MMP-1/TIMP-1 ratio is associated with increased type I collagen degradation. Potential mechanism contributing to the pathogenesis of exudative AMD	[1-4]
			Non-EMC Substrates Pro-MMP-1, Pro-MMP-2, proMMP-9, MCP-1, MCP-3, MCP-4, SDF, Pro-1L-1β, 1L-1β, IL-8, IGFBP-2, IGFBP-3, Pro-TNF-α, CXCL5, CXCL11 precursor, Casein, C1q, Serum amyloid A protein, α1-Proteinase Inhibitor, α1-Anti-Chymotrypsin, α2-Macroglobulin			Non-AMD Eye Processes - Corneal wound repair - Glaucomatous optic nerve head damage - Epiretinal and subretinal membranes in PVR - Activation of fibroblasts at the head of pterygium - Overexpression is related to poor RB differentiation	[4-7]
Collagenase-2	MMP-8	11q21-q22	EMC Substrates Collagen (I-III, V, VII, VIII, X), Gelatin, Fibronectin, Laminin Subunit Gamma-2, Entactin, Aggrecan, Tenascin, Brevican Core Protein Precursor, Myelin Basic Protein, Fibrinogen	The activation of osteoclasts, the enhancement of collagen affinity, β-FGF release, anti-inflammatory activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Corneal stroma ○ Tear samples ○ Vitreous samples 	AMD Eye Processes - Several roles in ocular inflammation and tissue remodeling, including cleavage degradation ECM components and regulation of cytokine activity	[4,8]
			Non-EMC Substrates			Non-AMD Eye Processes	

			Pro-MMP-8, MCP-1, Pro-TNF- α , IL-8, L-Selectin, IGFBP, CXCL5, CXCL10, CXCL11, Substance P, Angiotensin I, Angiotensin II, Bradykinin, Ephrin- B1, Plasmin C1-Inhibitor, α 1-Proteinase Inhibitor, α 2-Macroglobulin			- Xerophthalmia - In RD models low MMP-8 expression may lead to inhibition of RPE apoptosis and proliferation - Uveal Melanocytes may participate remodeling and inflammatory process via MMP-8	[4,8-11]
Collagenase-3	MMP-13	11q22.3	EMC Substrates	Cell migration, Ability of cleavage interstitial collagens I, II and III, as well as other ECM molecules. Key regulator of choroidal angiogenesis	o Corneal epithelium	Non-AMD Eye Processes	[4,8,12]
			Colagen (I-III, VI, VII, IX, X, XIV), Gelatin, Fibronectin, Laminin Subunit Gamma-2, Collagen telopeptides, SDF, Brevican, Fibrillin, Aggrecan, Perlecan, CTGF, Large Tenascin-C, Osteonectin, SPARC, Biglycan, Fibrinogen			- MMP-13 produced by bone marrow-derived cells appear to be important in experimental choroidal neovascular membrane formation	
			Non-EMC Substrates			Non-AMD Eye Processes	
			Pro-MMP-9, Pro-MMP-13, MCP-3, SDF, Pro-TNF- α , CXCL5, Factor XII, Casein, C1q, α 1-Anti-Chymotrypsin, α 2-Macroglobulin			- Corneal wound healing - Increased expression in experimental RD - The modulation of fibrosis could have implications for the development of PVR - MMP-13 expressed by pterygium tissues may induce collagen II and III remodeling in pterygium stroma (pterygium recurrence)	[4,6,8,13-14]
Gelatinases							
Gelatinase A	MMP-2	16q13	EMC Substrates	The growth of axons, cell migration, the differentiation of mesenchymal cell with inflammation phenotype, enhancement of collagen affinity, cell proliferation, migration of epithelial cells, anti-inflammatory, an increase in the bioavailability of TGF-b, neuronal	o Cornea (all layers) o Vitreous o Optic nerve head o Interphotorecept or matrix o Lens epithelium	AMD Eye Processes	[1,4,8,15-18]
			Collagen (I, II, III, IV, V, VII, X, XI), Gelatin, Elastin, Fibronectin, Entactin/Nidogen-1, Aggrecan, Decorin, Fibrillin, Fibulin 2, Laminin-5, Tenascin, SPARC, Vitronectin, Galectin-1, Galectin-3, Versican, BM-40, Brevican, Neurocan, CTGF, CSPG-4, Dystroglycan, PCPE-1, Link Protein, Osteonectin, Myelin Basic Protein,			- Critical role in the early AMD development, due to the accumulation of deposits under the RPE and increased synthesis of IV type collagen -Total levels of active MMP-2 are significantly reduced in BM from AMD patients - Increase plasma levels in PCV	

			Biglycan, Fibrin, Fibrinogen	apoptosis leading to neurodegeneration			
			Non-EMC Substrates			Non-AMD Eye Processes	
			Pro-MMP-1, Pro-MMP-2, Pro-MMP-13, MMP-12, MCP-3, SDF, Pro-TGF- β 1, Pro-TNF- α , Pro-IL-1 β , CXCL5, IGFBP-3, IGFBP-4, IGFBP-5, IGFBP-6, 14-3-3 protein, Big endothelin-1, Cystatin C, Follistatin-like 1, Alpha-actin-2, Pregnancy zone protein, Substance P, Decorin, IGFBP, Plasminogen receptor S100A10, proEMAP/p43, FGF-R1, MMIF, Thrombospondin-2, Plasminogen, α 1-Proteinase Inhibitor, α 1-Anti-Chymotrypsin, α 2-Macroglobulin			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Corneal wound repair and development - Glaucomatous optic nerve head damage - Vitreous liquefaction - Cataract formation - Uveitis - PDR and new blood vessels formation - MMP-2 inhibition may reduce VEGF expression and, thus, angiogenesis in retinoblastoma cell lines (Overexpression is related to poor RB differentiation) 	[4,7,8,19,20]
			EMC Substrates			AMD Eye Processes	
Gelatinase B	MMP-9	20q11.2-q13.1	Collagen (I, IV, V, XI, and XIV), Gelatin, Elastin, Vitronectin, Laminin, Decorin, Fibrillin, Fibronectin, SPARC, Aggrecan, Link Protein, Galectin-1, Galectin-3, Versican, Decorin, Biglycan, Link Protein, Osteonectin, Myelin Basic Protein, Fibrin, Fibrinogen	Collagen affinity enhancing, pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory activity, tumor cell resistance, IL-2 response reduction, hypertrophic chondrocyte apoptosis and the subsequent incorporation of new	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Corneal epithelium and stroma o Lens epithelium o Retinal ganglion cells o Iris o Ciliary body o vitreous 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased plasma levels in GA in AMD - Development of CNV as part of AMD pathogenesis - Increase plasma levels in PCV - Total levels of active MMP-9 are significantly reduced in BM from AMD patients 	[1,4,8,15-18]
			Non-EMC Substrates			Non-AMD Eye Processes	

			Pro-MMP-2, Pro-MMP-9, Pro-MMP-13, MCP-3, SDF, Pro-IL-8, Pro-TNF- α , Pro-TGF- β 2, Pro-IL-1 β , Cell-surface IL-2R α , CXCL5, CXCL9, CXCL10, CXCL11, FGF-R1, CTAP-III/NAP-2, GRO α , PF-4, Integrin beta-2, IGFBP- 1, IGFBP-4, Substance P, Angiotensin I, Angiotensin II, ADAMTS-4, SERPINE2, Casein, C1q, TFPI, Plasminogen, α 1-Proteinase Inhibitor, α 2-Macroglobulin	units of functional osteoblasts		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Corneal ulcerations and neovascularization - Vitreous liquefaction - Cataract formation - Uveitis - PDR and new blood vessels. An up regulation is associated with CNV. Might be involved in hemorrhagic transformation in patients affected with PDR. Accelerate apoptosis of retinal capillary cells. - MMP-9 inhibition may reduce VEGF expression and, thus, angiogenesis in retinoblastoma cell lines (Overexpression is related to poor RB differentiation) - 17β-estradiol upregulates MMP-9 in the lacrimal gland and conjunctival epithelium, increasing activity in tears of dry subjects - Is linked to and contributes to rod death in RP model 	[4,7,8,19-22]	
Stromelysins								
Stromelysin-1	MMP-3	11q23	EMC Substrates	Migration of cells, epithelial cells apoptosis, the formation of epithelial bubbles, epithelial-mesenchymal conversion, angiostatin-like elements generation, the collagen affinity enhancement, release of bFGF, increase in the bioavailability of IGF-1, cell proliferation, pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory activity, increase the bioavailability of TGF- β , disorder in cells aggregation, increase in cell invasiveness; release of VEGF and bFGF, upregulation of angiogenesis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Corneal stroma o Optic nerve head 	AMD Eye Processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The directional shift in the MMP-3/TIMP-1 ratio is associated with increased type I collagen degradation. This may be an important mechanism contributing to the pathogenesis of early exudative AMD 	[1,4,8]
			Non-EMC Substrates			Non-AMD Eye Processes		
			Pro-MMP-1, Pro-MMP-3, Pro-MMP-7, Pro-MMP-8, Pro-MMP-9, Pro-MMP- 13, MCP-1, MCP-2, MCP-3, MCP-4, SDF, Pro-TNF- α , L-selectin, Pro-HB- EGF, Pro-IL-1 β , Perlecan, Decorin, E-cadherin, IGFBP-3, Cm-Tf, Substance P, T-kininogen, Casein, C1q, uPA, uPAR, Osteopontin, VEGFA, PAI,					

			CXCL11, IGFBP-1, IGFBP-2, IGFBP-3, β 4-integrin, E-cadherin, Apo-A1, Apo-CII, CD95-L, Casein, Cm-Tf, Osteopontin, uPA, Plasminogen, Decorin, α 1-Proteinase Inhibitor, α 2-Macroglobulin	vasoconstriction and cell growth		- Elastic fibre degradation in patients with involuntal ectropion and entropion	
Metalloelastase	MMP-12	11q22.2-q22.3	EMC Substrates	May be involved in tissue injury and remodeling. Has significant elastolytic activity	o Corneal epithelium	- Increased expression in RD - Corneal wound healing - May be involved in the ECM remodeling - Key regulator of macrophage infiltration and inflammation, contributing to retinal vascular dysfunction and pathological angiogenesis. The increase or decrease of its levels facilitates CNV formation - The modulation of fibrosis could have implications for the development of PVR	[1,4, 28,29]
			Collagen (I, V, And IV), Gelatin, Elastin, Fibronectin, Vitronectin, Laminin, Entactin, Osteonectin, Decorin, Aggrecan, Biglycan, Fibrillin, Myelin Basic Protein, Fibrin, Fibrinogen				
			Non-EMC Substrates				
			Plasminogen, Pro-TNF- α , ApoA-1, CXCL9, CXCL10, CXCL11, uPAR, vWF, Factor XII, TFP1, α 1-Proteinase Inhibitor				
Matrilysin-2	MMP-26	11p15	EMC Substrates	Ability to digest ECM components	o epithelial conjunctiva cells	- Expression in glioma is correlated with poor clinical outcome	[4]
			Collagen IV, Gelatin, Fibronectin, Vitronectin, Fibrinogen				
			Non-EMC Substrates				
			Pro-MMP-9, Pro-MMP26, IGFBP-1, α 1-Proteinase Inhibitor, α 2-Macroglobulin				
Enamelysin	MMP-20	11q22.3	EMC Substrates	May play a central role in tooth enamel formation	o N/A	- Not associated with the appearance of exudative AMD, but it could affect the size of the neovascular lesion	[30]
			Collagen XVIII, Amelogenin, Ameloblastin, Aggrecan, Laminin, COMP				
			Non-EMC Substrates				
			Pro-MMP-20 (autolysis)				
Membrane-type MMPs (MT-MMP)							
MT-MMP-1	MMP-14	14q11-q12	EMC Substrates	Anti-inflammatory, cell migration, the formation of renal tubules, epithelial	o Corneal epithelium o Human TM cell culture, human	- Corneal infection, wound healing, inducing corneal neovascularization (pro-angiogenic factor)	[1,4, 25, 28,29]
			Collagen (I, II and III), Gelatin, Fibronectin, Tenascin, Vitronectin,				

			Laminin, Entactin, Galectin-3, CTGF-L, Fibrillin, Aggrecan, Perlecan, Syndecan-1, Lumican, Myelin Basic Protein, Fibrinogen	cell migration, adhesion reduction, flattening of the cells reduction, trailers embryo to the uterine epithelium	TM explant culture	- Proliferative diabetic retinopathy - Implications for ECM turnover - Biomarker of angiogenic activity in PDR - Keratinocyte migration	
			Non-EMC Substrates				
			Pro-MMP-2, Pro-MMP-13, Pro-MMP-14, MMP-14, MCP-3, SDF, Cell-surface CD44, RANKL, tTG, Pro-TNF- α , IL-8, HB-EGF, Factor XII, Pro- α v integrin chain, Apo-CII, Apo-E, α 1-Proteinase Inhibitor, α 2-Macroglobulin				
			EMC Substrates				
MT-MMP-2	MMP-15	15q13-q21	Fibronectin, Tenascin, Entactin, Laminin, Aggrecan, Perlecan, Proteoglycan, Myelin Basic Protein	Adhesion and cell flatterring reduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human TM cell culture, human TM explant culture 	Non-AMD Eye Processes -Could play a modulatory role in IOP homeostasis	[4,31 .32]
			Non-EMC Substrates				
			Pro-MMP-2, Cell-surface bound tTG, Pro-TNF- α				
			EMC Substrates				
MT-MMP-3	MMP-16	8q21	Collagen III, Gelatin, Fibronectin, Vitronectin, Laminin, Myelin Basic Protein	Adhesion and cell flatterring reduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human TM cell culture, human TM explant culture 	Non-AMD Eye Processes -Could play a modulatory role in IOP homeostasis	[4,31 .32]
			Non-EMC Substrates				
			Pro-MMP-2, Cell-surface bound tTG, Pro-TNF- α , Metastasis-suppressor KISS-1				
			EMC Substrates	May be involved in the activation of membrane-bound precursors of growth factors or inflammatory mediators, such as TNF- α . May also be involved in tumoral process.			
MT-MMP-4	MMP-17	12q24.3	Gelatin, Fibrin, Fibrinogen, Myelin Basic Protein		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human TM cell culture, human TM explant culture 	Non-AMD Eye Processes -Could play a modulatory role in IOP homeostasis	[4,31 .32]
			Non-EMC Substrates				
			Pro-MMP-2, Pro-TNF- α , HB-EGF, ADAMTS4 Peptidase				
MT-MMP-5	MMP-24	20q11.2	EMC Substrates			Non-AMD Eye Processes	

			Fibronectin, Gelatin, Chondroitin Sulphate Proteoglycan, Dermatan Sulphate Proteoglycan	Involved in cell-cell interactions between nociceptive neurites and mast cells. May play a role in axonal growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Human TM cell culture, human TM explant culture 	-Could play a modulatory role in IOP homeostasis	[4,31,32]
Tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinases (TIMPs)							
Metalloproteinase inhibitor 1	TIMP-1	Xp11.3	All types of MMPs (MMP-1, MMP-3, MMP-7 and MMP-9) and MT-MMPs	Connective tissue cells, macrophages Increased expression has been found associated with worse prognosis of tumors such as laryngeal carcinoma or melanoma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Corneal epithelium and endothelium Optic nerve head Retinal ganglion cells Vitreous IPM 	<p style="text-align: center;">AMD Eye Processes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential role for MMPs in the development of CNV in AMD. TIMP-1 promotes VEGF-induced neovascularization in the retina - Increase levels in patients with GA in AMD - Lower TIMP-3 levels are associated with higher TIMP-1 levels and the presence of GA in AMD 	[16,17,33,34]
						<p style="text-align: center;">Non-AMD Eye Processes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increased expression in experimental RD and PVR - Corneal wound healing, keratoconus - POAG 	[28,29,35,36]
Metalloproteinase inhibitor 2	TIMP-2	17q25.3	All types of MMPs (MMP-2)	Connective tissue cells, macrophages Important role in hippocampus and cognitive function It has an independent antiangiogenic effect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Corneal epithelium RPE Retinal ganglion cells IPM Vitreous 	<p style="text-align: center;">AMD Eye Processes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In combination with MMP-14, is involved in regulation of MMP-2. High levels of TIMP-2 inhibit MMP-2 activity- Potential role in AMD 	[16,17,33,34]
						<p style="text-align: center;">Non-AMD Eye Processes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential Biomarkers of RB progression - Increased expression in experimental RD and PVR - Corneal wound healing, keratoconus - POAG 	[7,28,29]
Metalloproteinase inhibitor 3	TIMP-3	22q12.3	All types of MMPs ADAM ADAMTS	Blocks the development of neovascularization by inhibiting the binding of VEGF to the VEGF receptor, Regulate local MMP to maintain rate of turnover and limit choroidal growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RPE BM Corneal epithelium Vitreous IPM 	<p style="text-align: center;">AMD Eye Processes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Excess TIMP-3, may retard BM renewal and result in the thickening. - Reduced TIMP-3 production, causes an increase in the amounts of various collagens and development of early dry AMD. Also increases ADAM/ADAMTs, which can be implicated in CNV formation in AMD -Mutations in this gene have been associated with the autosomal dominant disorder SFD 	[16,17,33,34]

				Fibroblasts, synovial cells		Non-AMD Eye Processes	[34,37]
						- Potential role in RP	
Metalloproteinase inhibitor 4	TIMP-4	3p25.2	MMP-1, MMP-2, MMP-3, MMP-7 and MMP-9	Role in the regulation of platelet aggregation, hormonal and endometrial tissue remodeling	○ Aqueous humor	Non-AMD Eye Processes	[36]
						- POAG	

Ref: references. MMP-1: matrix metalloproteinase 1; BM-40: basement-membrane protein 40; CTGF: CCN2 or connective tissue growth factor ; ECM: extracellular matrix ; IGF-1: insulin-like growth factor 1; MCP-1: Monocyte chemoattractant protein-1; SDF: stromal cell derived factor ; AMD: age-related macular degeneration; RPE: retinal pigment epithelium; IGFBP: insulin like growth factor binding protein; CXCL11 precursor: C-X-C motif chemokine 11; PARP1: Poly [ADP-ribose] polymerase 1; TNF- α : Tumor necrosis factor alpha; TIMP-1: metalloproteinase tissue inhibitor 1 ; RB: retinoblastoma; MMP-8: matrix metalloproteinase 8; β -FGF: basic fibroblast growth factor; RD: retinal detachment; MMP-13: matrix metalloproteinase 13; SPARC: Secreted protein acidic and rich in cysteine; PVR: proliferative vitreoretinopathy; MMP-2: matrix metalloproteinase 2; CSPG-4: chondroitin sulfate proteoglycan 4; PCPE-1: procollagen c-proteinase enhancer 1; PCV: polypoidal choroidal vasculopathy; PDR: proliferative diabetic retinopathy ; VEGF: vascular endothelial growth factor; proEMAP/p43: tumour-derived cytokine; FGF-R1: fibroblast growth factor receptor 1; MMIF: macrophage migration inhibitory factor; TGF-b: transforming growth factor beta; MMP-9: matrix metalloproteinase 9; IL: interleukin; FGF-R1: fibroblast growth factor receptor 1; CTAP-III/NAP-2: connective tissue-activating peptide III/neutrophil-activating peptide-2; GRO α : growth-regulated oncogene alpha; PF-4: platelet factor 4; ADAMTS-4: a disintegrin and metalloproteinase with thrombospondin motifs; SERPINE2: serpin family E member 2; TFPI: tissue factor pathway inhibitor; CNV: choroidal neovascularization; GA: geographic atrophy; RP: retinitis pigmentosa; MMP-3:matrix metalloproteinase 3; Pro-HB- EGF: heparin-binding epidermal growth factor-like growth factor; Cm-Tf: carboxymethylated transferrin; uPA: urokinase plasminogen activator; uPAR: urokinase plasminogen activator receptor ; MMP-10: matrix metalloproteinase 10; MMP-11: matrix metalloproteinase 11; N/A: not available; PAI-2: plasminogen activator inhibitor-2; MMP-7: matrix metalloproteinase 7; BLD: basal laminar and linear deposits; Fas-L: Fas ligand; Apo-A1: apolipoprotein A1; Apo-CII: apolipoprotein C-2;CD95-L: cluster of differentiation-95 ligand; MMP-12: matrix metalloproteinase 12; vWF: von Willebrand factor; MMP-26: matrix metalloproteinase 26; MMP-20: matrix metalloproteinase 20; COMP: cartilage oligomeric matrix protein; MMP-14: matrix metalloproteinase 14; CTGF-L: connective tissue growth factor-like; RANKL: receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B ligand; tTG: tissue transglutaminase; TM: trabecular meshwork; MMP-15: matrix metalloproteinase 15; IOP: intraocular pressure; MMP-16: matrix metalloproteinase 16; Metastasis-suppressor KiSS-1: metastasis-suppressor kisspeptin 1; MMP-17: matrix metalloproteinase 17; MMP-24: matrix metalloproteinase 24; IPM: interphotoreceptor matrix; ADAM: a disintegrin and metalloproteinase; ADAMTS: A Disintegrin-like And Metalloproteinase with ThromboSpondin motifs; TIMP-2: metalloproteinase tissue inhibitor 2; TIMP-3: metalloproteinase tissue inhibitor 3; TIMP-4: metalloproteinase tissue inhibitor 4; SFD: Sorsby's Fundus Dystrophy; POAG: primary open angle glaucoma.

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